

Exploiting Sophisticated Static Analysis for Verilog (Supplementary Material)

QINLIN CHEN, Nanjing University, China
NAIREN ZHANG, Nanjing University, China
JINPENG WANG, Nanjing University, China
JIACAI CUI, Nanjing University, China
TIAN TAN*, Nanjing University, China
XIAOXING MA, Nanjing University, China
CHANG XU, Nanjing University, China
JIAN LU, Nanjing University, China
YUE LI*, Nanjing University, China

This supplementary material accompanies the main paper, “Exploiting Sophisticated Static Analysis for Verilog”. It provides the full details of a complementary case study that is only briefly summarized in the main paper due to space constraints.

1 Snowballing Process in Analysis Suite: A Complementary Case Study

As noted in the main paper, to assess whether our findings on the snowballing process in the analysis suite generalize beyond the missing-reset client analysis, we conduct a complementary case study of dead-lock under the same evaluation methodology. Due to space constraints in the main paper, we defer the detailed result tables, figures, and explanations to this supplementary material. These results are reported in Table 1 and Figure 1, which correspond to Table 2 and Figure 7 in the main paper, respectively. Below, we explain the results shown in Table 1 and Figure 1.

Representative Analyses. Table 1 presents the results of the dead-lock analysis and its representative dependencies. Compared to missing-reset, deadlock analysis depends on a largely distinct set of underlying analyses. While missing-reset relies heavily on understanding client analyses (such as clocks, regs, and resets), deadlock analysis depends only on fundamental analyses, most of which focus on the synchronization characteristics of the hardware (i.e., the analyses illustrated in the bottom-left of Figure 3 in our paper), such as guards-outputs, guard-inputs, and simple-computation-model presented in this table.

Result Metrics. For the fundamental analyses shown in Table 1, we are unable to collect ground truth data to evaluate their effectiveness, as no suitable tools (e.g., instrumentation tools) are available to our knowledge. Ground truth can be obtained for understanding client analyses, since they predict synthesizer results, and open-source synthesizers are accessible. Nevertheless, the effectiveness of these fundamental analyses can be indirectly reflected in the dead-lock results in Table 1, as dead-lock depends on them. Additionally, we use statistics derived from these analyses to reveal hardware characteristics, typically involving Verilog’s synchronized processes that are relevant to dead-lock. The meanings of these statistics are explained in the table caption.

*Corresponding author.

Table 1. Results of the dead-lock analysis and its representative dependencies, ordered topologically by their dependencies, across 13 Verilog programs. Columns mainly correspond to programs, rows to analyses (except the Meta row, which lists lines of code and IR size for each program), and cells display the relevant statistics. The last column aggregates statistics from previous columns, using totals for Meta, cfg, and dead-lock while using averages for the remaining analyses. For def-use, #Uses/Data indicates the average number of times a variable (or net) is used, while #Defs/Data shows the average number of times a variable (or net) is defined. For guard-outputs, #Outputs/Guard reflects the average number of variables written by a synchronous process, while for fast-guard-inputs, #Inputs/Guard reflects the average number of variables read. For simple-computation-model, #Computation reflects the number of synchronized processes in the hardware design, as computations are abstracted from these processes. For dead-lock, since no ground truth exists, we present how many reported alarms are confirmed by developers in the format “#Reported (#Confirmed)”; unconfirmed alarms are false positives. If none of the reported alarms are confirmed, we omit “(#Confirmed).”

		XS	ziu	biv	FPC	ha3	riv	sev	pi2	dav	st1	sha	sd3	da5	summary
Meta	LoC	1821858	22290	13601	7751	7662	6832	3461	3049	2753	2553	2171	805	663	1895449
	LoIR	8261716	26554	25435	41065	16053	12309	5825	5747	3592	9429	2281	2428	1314	8413748
cfg	#Node	5020594	15308	14762	18641	8130	7035	3362	3170	2013	5844	1846	1434	768	5102907
	#Edge	4355660	14646	13773	24735	8583	6635	2892	3398	1799	5100	1932	1482	717	4441352
def-use	#Uses/Data	2.09	1.84	1.81	1.92	1.93	1.75	1.40	1.97	1.54	1.90	9.44	2.10	2.10	2.45
	#Defs/Data	1.06	1.13	1.11	1.20	1.11	1.08	0.97	1.23	0.97	1.54	8.67	1.27	1.29	1.74
guard-outputs	#Outputs/Guard	1.06	1.11	1.15	1.70	1.29	1.24	1.16	2.58	1.22	1.29	2.87	1.83	1.12	1.51
fast-guard-inputs	#Inputs/Guard	2.36	2.63	1.77	2.19	2.55	1.72	1.70	5.09	2.14	1.56	5.00	4.04	1.93	2.67
simple-computation-model	#Computation	1565452	2984	3490	371	1071	1544	1016	220	433	1740	30	176	186	1578713
dead-lock	#Reported	20	19	3	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	1	4 (1)	2 (1)	52 (2)

Analysis Results. Below, as in our paper’s discussion of how dependencies contribute to downstream clients for missing-reset, we explain how the dependencies listed in Table 1 support dead-lock, proceeding from top to bottom.

To aid understanding, we first recall two key aspects of dead-lock (introduced in Section 5.1.2 of our paper): (1) A dead-lock occurs when *synchronized Verilog processes* have *circular dependencies*. (2) A synchronized process P *depends on* another process Q if the output signal of Q is the input control signal of P .

The cfg analysis appears first. It provides control flow information, enabling precise identification of control signals for synchronized processes, which is a crucial step for the precision of the dead-lock algorithm.

The next three analyses are def-use, guard-outputs, and fast-guard-inputs. def-use supplies definition-use information to help guard-outputs and fast-guard-inputs determine the output and input signals of synchronized processes. fast-guard-inputs is a version that sacrifices some precision for improved speed. Initially, we explored a more precise implementation (precise-guard-inputs) due to concerns that false positive inputs might reduce the precision of dead-lock. However, we found that the fast version offers sufficient precision and significant speed benefits in practice, making it our preferred approach. This case, similar to the one in missing-reset, demonstrates that our analysis suite enables developers to explore alternatives and make practical trade-offs by offering a range of fundamental analyses.

Next is simple-computation-model, which abstracts synchronized processes as “*computations*”. This abstraction is designed to provide an appropriate granularity: if too fine-grained, precision of dead-lock improves but speed decreases; if too coarse-grained, precision becomes unacceptable. We acknowledge that the prefix “simple” may be misleading. It is the first implementation of a computation model in our suite, so we named it “simple” to distinguish it from potential future

versions. It is not necessarily simple in terms of precision or implementation complexity. We plan to rename it in the future to better reflect its characteristics.

Finally, `dead-lock` employs `simple-computation-model` to abstract synchronized processes, and leverages `cfg`, `fast-guard-inputs`, and `guard-outputs` to identify the input control signals and outputs of these processes, as well as to detect circular dependencies among them. Potential deadlocks are reported whenever such circular dependencies are found.

As shown in the table, `dead-lock` reports 52 alarms across 13 projects, with 2 confirmed bugs. This data is comparable to the results of `missing-reset`, which reports 110 alarms with 5 confirmed bugs. This further supports our observation that the number of alarms from our analyses is manageable.

Development Effort and Analysis Time. Figure 1 is obtained by running `dead-lock` on the XS program. Compared to the original figure in our paper, this setting triggers the execution of additional fundamental analyses to support the `dead-lock` analysis.

The figure is consistent with the main findings of our original case study: (1) Developing a new client becomes significantly easier by leveraging our analysis suite. The `dead-lock` analysis requires approximately 260 lines of code (LoC) to implement, while developing it and its dependencies from scratch would require about 5,000 LoC. For `missing-reset`, the numbers are 540 versus 9,700. (2) Fundamental analyses account for most of the workload. In this figure, they account for 90% ($= 30.8/34.0$); for `missing-reset`, the proportion is 94%. (3) Overall performance remains practical. The `dead-lock` analysis completes in 34 seconds on a million-line codebase, while `missing-reset` takes 74.3 seconds.

Fig. 1. `dead-lock` on a large-scale RISC-V SoC (XS from Table 1).